

IMPLEMENTATION OF EXPERT JIGSAW IN TEACHING LITERATURE TO SELECTED GRADE 11 STUDENTS OF TUNASAN NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

Results from PISA shows that the Philippines is one of the lowest-scoring countries in the world in terms of the students' reading comprehension. This study aimed to find out whether the Jigsaw technique could be used to develop reading comprehension among students when exposed to different literature from the Philippines. An Explanatory-Sequential design was used to determine the pre-test, post-test scores, differences between scores, and the themes surrounding student learning experience during the experiment. Pre-test was used prior to the implementation, while post-test was used to determine if there is a significant difference in terms of their scores. To further expand the results, the researchers used focus group discussions consisting of semi-structured questions to find the learning experiences of the students.

Keywords: *Collaborative Learning; Expert Jigsaw; Philippine Literature; Reading Comprehension*

INTRODUCTION

Reading comprehension is one of the most important factors that a student will develop in a school. However, the Philippines is known for being one of the lowest ranking countries when the Reading Comprehension of the students were measured (PISA, 2022). To further develop the competency of the students, Lathan (2019) suggests that

implementing learning strategies would be effective. The popular Expert Jigsaw technique was created by Elliot Aronson and aims to foster collaboration among students by having shared objectives and encouraging interaction. Forming a healthy environment inside a classroom setting lessens the competition and encourages collaboration.

Reading and comprehension skills are a combination of competencies needed for students to be able to understand and comprehend what the text is all about fully. It is one of the most complex behaviors in which humans engage. By merely reading the text without understanding the meaning that lies in it, it can be worthless and give an empty feeling to the readers, students may be unable to extract the central idea and information that a text has. The ability to recognize the main concept of the text is a necessary skill that enables students to understand the central meaning of the text and to interpret it correctly. By this, students can better understand the subject they are reading (Idulog, et al., n.d). Reading is complex yet central to any English language program. It is a skill that involves learners entirely in the learning process as it depends on prior knowledge and connects it with the reading tasks at hand (Al-Hadal, 2020; Alenezi, 2021; Al-Kadi & Hamdi, 2022; Suchona & Urmy, 2019; Van, 2021). Reading, listening, writing, and speaking are the four language skills that are important in the process of learning, and by employing and integrating these four skills in the process a person will completely learn, but Carrel et al., (1988) and Zhang (2008) said that among these four, reading skills is the most important skill and must be mastered in English as a second or foreign language. Reading plays a conclusive role in molding the educational future of students and more importantly in achieving academic goals than the other language skills (Gisler and Eberts, 2009). In getting information and knowledge through texts, reading, and comprehension is a very necessary skill needed to understand the meaning of the texts and these interrelated skills will also determine the student's academic performance (Dawkins, 2017).

Teaching reading comprehension can enable the students to understand what they read, to increase students' understanding. Expert Jigsaw is one of the student-centered teaching strategies that are collaborative and can be used in improving the reading comprehension of the learners. Cooperative learning makes the students work together and will give them an equal opportunity to learn. By interacting with others, they can improve their communication, problem-solving, and critical thinking skills that they can use to comprehend the texts that are given to them (Rashed, 2022). Aronson developed the Jigsaw technique and argues that by providing each member of the group with an important role to play in activities, learning the material through a collaborative teaching style will promote listening, writing, and reading.

Aronson and Bridgeman (1979) have argued that competitiveness inside the classroom has been one of the primary reasons why learners rarely cooperate with each other. Eventually, the students were taught to participate in collaborative learning and as a result, children progressively learn that the old competitive behaviors are no longer suitable by using this "Jigsaw" strategy. Cooperative learning is a type of strategy that stimulates a child's active learning skills (Yimer & Feza, 2019). However, Liao (2005) has stated that competition can still be seen in collaborative learning. But unlike the

competition on the nature of traditional learning, cooperative learning strives to establish an environment in which team members have high expectations of one another. For the reason that collaborative learning requires the students to be expertise in their assigned portion of learning, which they will later on discuss with their certain groups (Costouros, 2020).

The results from the Programme for International Student Assessment (2021) indicates that Filipinos need improvements. This issue needs to be addressed by improving reading comprehension at an evaluative level while teachers should focus on enhancing higher order thinking skills. The students' development is affected if their reading comprehension continues to decline. Developing an adequate reading comprehension can be complicated but with the help of cooperative learning, the students can establish a good foundation in advancing their reading comprehension.

Research Questions

The Philippines is one of the lowest-scoring countries in the world in terms of the students' reading comprehension. Because of that, it is important to understand how to improve the reading comprehension of the students. This study asks how Implementation of Expert Jigsaw strategy impacts the comprehension of the students. Specifically, it aims to answer:

1. What were the pre-test scores of the Controlled group and Experimental group?
2. What were the post test scores of the Controlled group and Experimental group?
3. Was there a significant difference between the post-test scores of the controlled and experimental groups?
4. What are the learning experiences of Grade 11 ICT students of Tunasan National High School upon the implementation of the Jigsaw strategy?

To further analyze the result of the implementation, the researchers hypothesized that there is no significant difference in the results of the controlled group to the experimental group. The researchers also assumed that: (1) There will be a decrease in the percentage of failure of the students, (2) students would retain more knowledge, (3) significant increase in the level of the students' active participation, (4) Improvement in the students' cooperation and better comprehension of the students.

METHODOLOGY

Scope and Delimitation

The study focused on grade 11 students of Tunasan National High School, specifically Information Communication and Technology and Home Economics. It includes specific lessons from the subject '21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World.' The researchers were given five (5) days to implement the Expert Jigsaw

to the Grade 11 ICT students of Tunasan National High School, and two (2) separate days to administer the pre-test and post-test across all groups. The duration of the implementation per day was 35 minutes.

Research Design

An Explanatory-sequential research design was employed by the researchers through experimentation for quantitative data. Furthermore, phenomenological studies are used in quasi-experimental research for quantitative data and thematic analysis is utilized in qualitative data collected through semi-structured Focus Group Discussion interviews.

Population and Sampling

The participants of the study are students of Tunasan National High School, specifically, three sections from Grade 11 Information Communication and Technology (ICT) students as the experimental group and three sections from Grade 11 Home Economic (HE) students for the controlled group, all of which have 17 students per class.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering started by asking permission to conduct the study using experimentation from the school head of Tunasan National High School. The study consisted of two strand participants namely, ICT, and HE. Three (3) sections are gathered from each strand. HE (a total of three sections) is the controlled group while the strand of ICT (three sections) underwent the Expert Jigsaw strategy. The data gathering was followed by the conduction of pre-tests to assess the current learning of the students. The actual experiment then commenced through assignment of small groups of students. Learning and reading materials were provided throughout the duration of the study. Afterwards, the researchers provided post-test with the same number of questions as the pre-test to both the experimental and controlled groups. The results were first interpreted using statistical treatment, followed by the interpretation of the analytic results through thematic analysis. Researchers followed a 7 step-procedure to gather a smooth flow of data when implementing the Expert Jigsaw strategy.

Instrumentation

The researchers administered expert-validated researcher-made examinations to find out and assess the students' knowledge about Philippine Literature in line with the provided lessons on the subject of "21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World". The pre-test and post-test consisted of 30 items, allowing the researchers to compare the results after the experimentation and to know if there is no significant difference. The researchers also printed five (5) different Philippine selections which were given to the students throughout the experimentation; it serves as their reading material for the whole session. To further understand the effectiveness of Expert Jigsaw and gather data, the researchers also conducted a focus group discussion with semi-structured interview questions, consisting of 6 students from the experimental sections.

Statistical Treatment for Quantitative Data

The t-test and mean were employed by the researchers as the statistical treatment for the quantitative data. The average score for the pre-tests and post-tests for the conventional and experimental groups was calculated by analyzing the mean. Conversely, the t-test was employed by the researchers to examine and ascertain the difference in the post-test scores between the conventional and experimental groups.

Analysis for Qualitative Data

The researchers utilized thematic analysis as the statistical treatment for the qualitative data. It is applied to inspect the patterns derived from the experiences of the respondents upon the implementation of the Expert Jigsaw. Codes and themes were derived from the statements of the participants during the interview.

RESULTS

Table 1

SOP 1. Mean score results on pre-test of both controlled group and experimental group.

Variable	Mean	Interpretation	Variable	Mean	Interpretation
HE1	13.352	Good	ICT1	14.941	Good
HE2	12.588	Poor	ICT2	12.882	Poor
HE3	13	Good	ICT3	12.705	Good

Table 2

SOP 2. Post test score of the controlled group and experimental group.

Variable	Mean	Interpretation	Variable	Mean	Interpretation
HE1	12.117	Poor	ICT1	15.058	Good
HE2	11.058	Poor	ICT2	14.352	Good
HE3	11.529	Poor	ICT3	14.294	Good

The researchers implemented the expert jigsaw technique to the students. Furthermore, to find out if the expert jigsaw technique is effective, the researchers computed the mean score on the post test scores of both controlled group and experimental group. As an outcome, the Table 2 statistical analysis showed that the average mean of the experimental group is higher than the controlled group. The three sections of the experimental group have an average mean of 15.058 interpreted as good, 14.352 interpreted as good, and 14.294 interpreted as good. Meanwhile, the sections of the controlled group have an average mean of 12.117, 11.058, and 11.529 which are all interpreted as poor.

Table 3

SOP 3. P-Value of Post-test

Value	P-Value	Interpretation
HE1 and ICT1	0.020	There is a significant difference
HE2 and ICT2	0.008	There is a significant difference
HE3 and ICT3	0.025	There is a significant difference

After the researchers computed the post test scores of both controlled group and experimental group, Table 3 showed that there is a significant difference between the two concluding the p-values: $(0.020 < 0.05)$, $(0.008 < 0.05)$, and $(0.025 < 0.05)$.

The experimental groups scored higher than those in the controlled group, with the controlled group continuing in the traditional way of teaching while the experimental group implemented the Expert Jigsaw technique. As stated in the Null Hypothesis, there is no significant difference in the results of the controlled group to the experimental group. Hence, the researchers reject the null hypothesis.

Graph 1

SOP 4: Learning experiences of the students

The Expert Jigsaw technique was utilized to introduce different reading selections to the students of ICT. Upon the implementation of the strategy, the students underwent different learning experiences. The assumptions made by the researchers were correct. The students experienced “Active participation”, “Collaboration”, “Comprehension”, and “Confidence.” In the end of the study, it concludes that the learning experiences of the students which are the student’s participation and collaboration eventually results in a better comprehension of the students about their topics and at the end it gives the students confidence in class.

DISCUSSION

The pre-test results show that most of the students are able to proficiently answer the questions in the examination. This finding is congruent to the pre-test results shown in the study of Dacosta and Fabella (2023). It indicates that although the materials have not been taught before the test, their prior knowledge about the selections helped them to answer the 30-item test. Hailikari et al. stated that the prior knowledge of the student is the most important factor that influences their learning and achievement (2008).

On the other hand, the post-test results show an increase in the performance of the students who experienced the Expert Jigsaw technique. This finding is also observed in the study of Jainal and Shahrill (2021) which found improvements in the performance

of the students exposed to the strategy. This was also found similar to the study of Yemi et al., indicating that the Jigsaw strategy is more effective compared to traditional methods.

The significant differences in the scores of the students shows improvement in their comprehension of the materials. In a similar study, the findings of Ulfah (2014) shows that the usage of the expert jigsaw can be useful to improve students' comprehension of narrative texts. The result of Ulfah's study presented a significance level of 5%, the t-test (to) value was greater than the t-table (tt) ($17.1 > 1.991$). As per the test criteria, the findings indicated a noteworthy distinction in students' reading comprehension proficiency when they used the jigsaw technique versus when they did not. The jigsaw method's distinctive feature is that it lets students start where they feel most comfortable, allowing them to engage and conduct discussions with peers who share their knowledge. Students must instruct their fellow classmates as part of the second component, which evaluates the effectiveness of their learning (Norintan, 2008). Furthermore, Benware and Deci (1984) explained that learning to teach causes people to learn more actively. He discovered that compared to pupils who learn merely to pass tests, those who learn to teach had higher conceptual learning scores and are more motivated to learn.

The researchers observed that there is an increase in the level of participation and cooperation of the learners. More importantly, the students have improved their reading comprehension as well as their self-confidence whenever there is an ongoing discussion during the implementation. These are aligned to the results of Nurbianta and Dahlia (2018) that the reading skills of the students can be improved as long as the students' motivation are boosted with the aid of cooperative learning in the form of expert jigsaw. Furthermore, Benware (1984) explained that learning to teach causes people to learn more actively. He discovered that compared to pupils who learn merely to pass tests, those who learn to teach had higher conceptual learning scores and are more motivated to learn. The Jigsaw technique can make the learners active once it is applied to the classroom set-up of the students. It establishes a sense of responsibility because each member contributes equally to the structure of the groupings (Gladstone, 2013; Klippel, 1984).

The Jigsaw teaching method promotes collaboration and discussion, as well as self-motivated learning strategies that teach students to seek answers to their questions to clear misunderstandings and correct their perception about certain things that will effectively give them academic gains or knowledge on how they are going to analyze and solve the problem they have (Twamala, 2021). In 2018, Johnson and Johnson stated that in cooperative learning, students are tasked to perform in groups, and they get more opportunities to interact with their fellow classmates and expand on their individual knowledge. This not only improves their analytical and emotional skills to do the task assigned, but they also learn to gather and distribute their resources amongst themselves. In collaborative learning it does not mean that the focus is solely on collaborating with another to acquire knowledge, by implementing different activities under this method, students are given a responsibility to help and contribute to the group. They have their own tasks in the group that will help them gain self-learning and

strengthen their ability to think critically and solve problems effectively, so that they make a good contribution as an individual.

Conclusions

The researchers analyzed all of the gathered data and as a result, it showed that there is a significant difference between the post-test scores of both the controlled and experimental sections of the study. Experimental sections obtained a higher score in their post-test than their pre-test scores, it can be said that the impact of using the Jigsaw strategy in the three experimental sections helped them improve their scores and made them learn better. That made them acquire a high score. On the other hand, the Jigsaw strategy opens the door of improvement in the various skills of students who have participated in this experiment; they learn how to improve their involvement and cooperation, which will give them a better ability to comprehend concepts and texts that increase their self-confidence and involve them more actively in discussions. This also allows them to be an active student in the group, share their views and ideas, ask questions as well as become responsible students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers recommend (1) the students to engage themselves in various learning strategies like the Expert Jigsaw Strategy to further enhance their collaborative learning skills, (2) the teachers, school administrators, and government agencies to establish programs that elaborate the importance of learning strategies, such as Expert Jigsaw, and explore and utilize it to ameliorate the learner's class participation. Teachers are encouraged to give students the proper motivation and stimulation that can aid in the student's participation during the classroom setting. Most importantly, future researchers are recommended to designate students into their home groups prior to the implementation of the study to enable the facilitator to maximize the allotted time for the strategy and create an opportunity for an in-depth discussion or sharing about the assigned topic or selection. The proper intervention of the teacher-in-charge and initiation from a student within a group also plays a crucial role in achieving the active participation from the learners. Researchers also recommend that the Expert Jigsaw strategy is implemented with well-equipped materials such as the reading materials and research instruments which are planned ahead of the study's execution. Ultimately, future researchers can lengthen the experimentation process to determine its outcome if it is implemented in a longer duration.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers applied **informed consent**, **confidentiality**, and **anonymity** throughout the duration of the study. The researchers asked for a formal letter consenting

to the execution of the experimentation. In addition, all staff and students involved in the study are informed about the context, goal, and procedure of the research and were not asked for their personal information. Any information given by the students and staff are kept in a laptop that is only accessible by the proponents of the research. The raw data gathered are then carefully disposed of after it is interpreted. These are in accordance with the **Data Privacy Act of 2012**.

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